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Designing Low-Temperature Synthesis Methods for 2-Dimensional Oxide Perovskites

A Data Management Plan created with DMP Assistant

Data Management Planning Expert Group

Information

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Template: Portage Template

Project abstract: This data management plan was created by the Smith lab at the University of Waterloo as a standard for lab projects. This particular project is developing new synthetic techniques for synthesizing Two-dimensional perovskites at lower temperatures and with shorter reaction times. It integrates data from multiple characterization techniques including Raman microscopy, XRD, XPS, and electron microscopy. This DMP demonstrates potential approaches to data management for research projects focused on sample analysis and using multiple different data collection techniques.

Start date: 30-09-2021

End date: 30-08-2023

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Data Collection

What types of data will you collect, create, link to, acquire and/or record?

Raw data files are captured in a number of file formats, including:

- Photographs will be created as either JPG or PNG files, each of which enable ease of sharing.
- Raman data (both single spectra and variable temperature series) is collected through WiRE 5.5 in Renishaw PLC's proprietary WDF file format. A secondary copy of the data will be saved as a comma separated value (CSV) file to facilitate sharing and expand access.
- XRD data is collected on a range of instruments, including at least three manufacturers (Bruker, INEL, and Panalytical) with different proprietary data formats. All data will be exported as CSV files to facilitate sharing and ensure ease of access.
- XAS data is acquired at synchrotron facilities and stored in CSV files.
- OriginPro files use a proprietary OPJ format. The data are too complex to export in any other format.
- Jupyter Notebooks (IPYNB files) are built on open-source software, making them readily accessible to anyone.
- All information will be saved in ASCII text format to maximize accessibility.

What file formats will your data be collected in? Will these formats allow for data re-use, sharing and long-term access to the data?

Open and proprietary data formats will be collected. Additionally, some data is gathered in paper, whereas others are collected via devices or samples. All data collected via paper will be transcribed to REDCap, and any proprietary format will be saved as open formats in addition. Further description, including all file formats matched to data types described earlier, is included in internal documentation available to the research team.

What conventions and procedures will you use to structure, name and version-control your files to help you and others better understand how your data are organized?

All individual files start with date, data collectors' initials, the number of their lab notebook in which the experiment is described, the page number of the lab notebook where the experiments are described and then a concise description of the experiment. For example: RS1001-Sample1 is sample one in RS's book 1, page 001.

Once the experiments are complete, the data and data files will be integrated into the research team's sample and characterization databases.

Project folders will be systematically structured across the team. Researchers are expected to save their data under proper subfolders using the following folder structure:

Folder structure:	Example:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">User's name<ul style="list-style-type: none">Experiment type<ul style="list-style-type: none">Lab Notebook Location<ul style="list-style-type: none">README fileAnalysis files (starting with date of analysis in ISO format)<ul style="list-style-type: none">Raw data<ul style="list-style-type: none">Original, unmodified data filesProcessed data<ul style="list-style-type: none">Data files that have been modified (for example, by baseline subtraction)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Xinran Liu<ul style="list-style-type: none">Variable Temperature Raman<ul style="list-style-type: none">XL1001-Sample1<ul style="list-style-type: none">README.txtYYYY-MM-DD-XL-1001-Sample1-vtRamanAnalysis.xlsxYYYY-MM-DD-XL-1001-Sample1-vtRamanAnalysis.pptx<ul style="list-style-type: none">Raw data<ul style="list-style-type: none">YYYY-MM-DD-XL-1001-Sample1-Scan1a.wdf<ul style="list-style-type: none">Processed dataYYYY-MM-DD-XL-1001-Sample1-Scan1a-proc.wdf<ul style="list-style-type: none">Single Raman Spectra<ul style="list-style-type: none">XL1001-Sample2<ul style="list-style-type: none">README.txtYYYY-MM-DD-XL-1001-Sample2-RamanAnalysis.xlsxYYYY-MM-DD-XL-1001-Sample2-RamanAnalysis.pptx<ul style="list-style-type: none">Raw dataYYYY-MM-DD-XL-1001-Sample2-Scan1a.wdf<ul style="list-style-type: none">Processed dataYYYY-MM-DD-XL-1001-Sample2-Scan1a-proc.wdf

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation will be needed for the data to be read and interpreted correctly in the future?

Information regarding the sample being analyzed, the experimental conditions, and the analytical process are all logged per sample. Data files contain a unique sample ID for the material being studied, the name of the researcher who collected and analyzed the data, the composition of the sample, any common names by which the sample is known, the synthesis protocol, a photograph (if applicable), the location in which the sample is stored, experimental acquisition settings for the experiment, and any digital object identifiers (DOIs) that may exist for publication of the research or data online.

Each individual dataset will have a README file placed in the parent folder to summarize pertinent information. The README file will contain information regarding the dataset, including an overview of data files, methodological information that is not available in the individual data files, data-specific information for the files in each dataset, and information regarding any potential sharing or access restrictions.

How will you make sure that documentation is created or captured consistently throughout your project?

Researchers have their own physical lab notebooks. They are used to record the detailed steps of their experiments, including date, experiment procedures, chemical usage, results, and other information if necessary. Documentation from lab notebooks is later uploaded into the research team databases. Research group members can access a lab wiki for training, procedure, and reference material.

All complete and scientifically useful data will be stored in the Smith Research Group sample information and characterization databases so that the data can be safely stored and quickly accessed. These custom databases are built using a local installation of MongoDB, an open-source database software package. Characterization data is linked to sample information using unique sample codes.

The database provides the group with flexibility to co-locate information from a diverse set of requirements for individual techniques. Taking Raman microscopy data as an example, the stored data are logged using characterization codes, with information such as sample ID, sample user, file name, instruments, measurement mode, laser information, objective information, a copy of the raw data, a copy of fully processed data, and individual peaks obtained through peak-fitting. All information in the database uses ASCII text format to maximize accessibility.

If you are using a metadata standard and/or tools to document and describe your data, please list here.

To enter data into the database, research team members use a custom in-house software package that screens data submissions for completeness and accuracy. This software package rejects any entries that do not have complete data and mandatory metadata entries. Entry of information into the in-house database is a two-step process:

- i. Metadata describing the sample is entered,
- ii. Characterization data is entered. Four types of characterization data can be uploaded to the database: Raman spectroscopy, infrared spectroscopy, x-ray diffraction, and x-ray absorption diffraction.

Completion of step (i) is verified every time before step (ii) can be attempted. The absence of mandatory metadata or files provided in the wrong format will result in rejection from the database. There are annotations to make sure all the information is uploaded in the correct format. The metadata describing the experimental protocols is logged alongside the data, with most data parameters automatically read from the original proprietary data fields to minimize chance of data entry error. After group members upload the data to the database, they will receive a documentation file containing the metadata they entered.

Required metadata for the databases includes:

- The unique sample ID,
- The elemental composition,
- The conventional name of the sample,
- Keywords/tags describing the sample (for database searching purposes),
- The synthesis protocol,
- The name of the data collector,
- The location at which the sample is stored, and
- Whether any sample remains available.

Optional metadata includes:

- A photograph of the sample
- Published article DOIs
- Published dataset DOIs

Datasets published to the University of Waterloo Dataverse will include citation metadata using the DublinCore standard.

Storage and Backup

What are the anticipated storage requirements for your project, in terms of storage space (in megabytes, gigabytes, terabytes, etc.) and the length of time you will be storing it?

Individual data files range from approximately 1 MB (most CSV files) up to approximately 100 MB for large OriginPro files. The data generated over the lifetime of the project will be about including backups that will be in the range of 15-30 GB. Data entered in the database will be kept indefinitely.

Understanding the size and magnitude of your research data helps you to understand both active storage needs, as well as those relating to data deposit and long-term preservation.

How and where will your data be stored and backed up during your research project?

Raw data is saved on dedicated instrument PCs after each measurement. Data is then transferred by the collector to a University of Waterloo Institutional Microsoft OneDrive used by the research team that is managed by the Principal Investigator (PI) and to which project members have full access.

Once data is processed and analyzed, processed data and corresponding raw data will be uploaded into the group database. The database is mirrored on two in-house servers at the University of Waterloo. Backups of the entire database are created on a nightly basis, alternating servers each day. A copy of the backups is downloaded on a monthly basis to the PI's computer. When the project is published, associated data will be deposited in the University of Waterloo Dataverse.

[University of Waterloo Dataverse Collection](#), part of Borealis, the Canadian Dataverse Repository: This is a data repository for research outputs of University of Waterloo faculty, students, and staff. Files are held in a secure environment on Canadian servers, and researchers can choose to make content available to the public, to specific individuals, or to keep it private. Depositing data in Dataverse supports open discovery, management, sharing, and preservation of research data.

How will the research team and other collaborators access, modify, and contribute data throughout the project?

Research team members and collaborators are given an account from the Principal Investigator to access the database through MongoDB access tools, including MongoDB Compass, using

python and the MongoDB package within Jupyter Notebooks, or through the group's custom software interface.

Preservation

Where will you deposit your data for long-term preservation and access at the end of your research project?

It is anticipated that all data will reside on the in-house server until the servers are decommissioned. Data will be posted on the Waterloo Dataverse Collection whenever portions of the research are published in academic venues, or suitable commercial protection (patent or data sharing agreement) is acquired.

Indicate how you will ensure your data is preservation ready. Consider preservation-friendly file formats, ensuring file integrity, anonymization and de-identification, inclusion of supporting documentation.

Data for all individual experiments will be exported in non-proprietary formats, such as simple ASCII text files, that contain all relevant metadata and sample information for that experiment. The mongoDB database is based on open source software and used for multiple ongoing projects in the lab. The Waterloo Dataverse offers long-term data preservation as part of Borealis, The Canadian Dataverse Repository. Borealis publishes a [preservation plan](#) online.

Sharing and Reuse

What data will you be sharing and in what form? (e.g. raw, processed, analyzed, final).

It is anticipated that fully processed data will be uploaded to the Waterloo Dataverse Collection in simple text format after publication of the research. Submissions to Dataverse may be embargoed to ensure data is protected prior to publication. Raw data may be made available to other researchers upon request. Analysis of the results will be available in published manuscripts.

Have you considered what type of end-user license to include with your data?

The data will be published with [Attribution 4.0 International](#) Creative Commons License (CC BY 4.0). All published data is open to the public for sharing and adapting.

What steps will be taken to help the research community know that your data exists?

Submission of the data to the Waterloo Dataverse Collection will generate a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) for the data, which will be posted on our website alongside the manuscript DOI. Wherever possible, the data DOI will also be inserted into published manuscripts.

Responsibilities and Resources

Identify who will be responsible for managing this project's data during and after the project and the major data management tasks for which they will be responsible.

Under the guidance of the Principal Investigator, highly qualified personnel associated with the project will create the data, process it, store it in the database, and submit it to Dataverse. The Principal Investigator will manage the in-house database and ensure that it is properly maintained and functional.

How will responsibilities for managing data activities be handled if substantive changes happen in the personnel overseeing the project's data, including a change of Principal Investigator?

All personnel on the project have training in accessing and contributing to the database. Should the Principal Investigator become unavailable, the research team will have full access to the data. This information could be downloaded and stored as suitable.

What resources will you require to implement your data management plan? What do you estimate the overall cost for data management to be?

The data management plan is based on the existence of two servers, each costing approximately \$5,000. These servers, which are currently 2 and 5 years old, are already installed and will need upgrades or replacements within a 5-year timeframe. Personnel in the group are trained to manage data as part of their regular research duties.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

If your research project includes sensitive data, how will you ensure that it is securely managed and accessible only to approved members of the project?

No sensitive data is included in this project.

If applicable, what strategies will you undertake to address secondary uses of sensitive data?

No sensitive data is included in this project.

How will you manage legal, ethical, and intellectual property issues?

Any legal, ethical, and intellectual properties issues will be guided by relevant policies of the University of Waterloo, such as [UW Policy 73 – Intellectual Property Rights](#), and the Laws of Canada. In some cases the data may form part of a patent application, in which case data will not be shared prior to the patent being granted.

Researchers associated with the project will be permitted to maintain copies of unpublished data with the restriction that the Principal Investigator is consulted and explicit permission be obtained in writing prior to sharing or publication of the data with individuals or organizations not associated with the project.

